

The Legal Implications of "Perverse, Arbitrary, and Mala Fide" as Explicit Grounds for Challenging Credit Ratings in India

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Abstract: Recently, the Delhi High Court delineates and circumscribes the scope of liability of Credit Ratings Agencies in the case of *Jindal Power Limited v. ICRA Limited*. The HC remarkably enumerated the grounds on which companies can challenge ratings issued by CRAs. The Court reasoned that CRAs provide expert opinions, with which the Court cannot interfere unless they are proved to be 'perverse, arbitrary and mala fide'. Additionally, the case clarifies that CRAs are bound to observe the obligations as mentioned in the regulations and the same cannot be done away with by agreements concluded between the client and the CRA. This means that the court enumerates other grounds for suing a Credit Rating Agency before the court in India. Hence, the parameter for the court to interfere and entertain the disputes arising out of rating are based on those three grounds. Henceforth, the purpose of this Article analyzes the significance and potential implications of providing 'perverse, arbitrary and mala fide' as explicit grounds for challenging the ratings before the Court and its effects in India.

Keywords: Perverse, Arbitrary, Mala fide, Credit Rating Agencies, Grounds for challenging ratings, CRAs Liability, Evolutions of CRAs, Court jurisdictions

1.0 INTRODUCTION

1.1 CREDIT RATING MEANING

According to Cambridge Dictionary Credit Rating simply means the calculation of the ability of a person, business, or government to pay their debts¹. Encyclopedia of Banking & Finance' by Charles J. Woelfel² states that a credit rating is a letter or number used by a mercantile or other agency in reports and credit rating books to denote the ability and disposition of various businesses (individual, proprietorship, partnership or corporation) to meet their financial obligations. It also states that ratings are used as a guide to the investment quality of bonds and stocks, based on the security of principal and interest (or dividends), earning power, mortgage position, market history, and marketability.

The term Credit Rating Agencies (hereinafter referred to as CRAs) is defined under Regulation 2(h) of the SEBI (Credit Rating Agencies) Regulations of 1999 to mean a body corporate which is engaged in or proposes to be engaged in the business of rating of securities offered by way of public or right issue.

1.2 EVOLUTION OF CREDIT RATING

In 1841, the first Mercantile Credit Agency was founded by Loius Tappan in New York which rated Merchants' ability to pay their financial obligation. Robert Dun created its first rating guide in 1859 subsequently after-acquired it. John Bradstreet established a similar organization and issued his rating guide in 1857. In 1933, these two organizations united to establish Dun & Bradstreet, which in 1962 purchased Moody's Investor Service. Moody's was founded by Moody in 1900. Standard & Poor's, another well-known rating agency, was founded in 1941 by combining the Standard Statistics Company and the Poor's Publishing Company, both of which had their origin earlier. Credit ratings were created largely to evaluate the creditworthiness of corporate borrowers that borrowed money from the general public instead of going to a bank³.

¹ See Definition of credit rating from the Cambridge Business English Dictionary © Cambridge University Press. Available at: <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/credit-rating>

² See CHARLES J. WOELFEL ENCYCLOPEDIA OF BANKING & FINANCE (1996)

³ Richard Cantor & Frank Parker (1994), The Credit Rating Industry: FRBNY Quarterly Review pg 1&2

Initially, agencies provided a free public rating of issuers and funded their operations primarily through the sale of publications and related resources. Since all of these companies were publishing books of financial information, they all naturally adopted the standard model for earning revenue from books; selling the rating manual to buyers (bond investors). In modern parlance, theirs was an 'investor pays business model for generating a revenue stream that would pay for ratings. Early in the 1970s, this business model changed to what it is today an 'issuer pays model whereby the issuer of the bonds pays the CRA for rating the bonds (Sudhanshu Kumar & Alok Verma, 2021)⁴.

1.3 EMERGING OF CREDIT RATING AGENCIES IN INDIA

In the late 1980s, CRAs emerged in India., In 1987, the first credit rating agency in India, CRISIL (Credit Rating and Information Services (India) Limited, was established. Presently, there are seven CRAs registered with SEBI namely, CRISIL, Fitch Ratings India Private Ltd., Investment Information and Credit Rating Agency ("ICRA"), Brickwork Rating India Pvt Ltd., Infomeric Valuation and Rating Pvt Ltd, and SME Rating Agency of India Ltd, ("SMERA") Credit Analysis & Research Ltd ("CARE").

2. STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

The credit rating is efficiently a precondition for bond market access and also the minimum requirement for listing a corporate debt on the stock exchange. It has been well recognized and accepted position that credit rating quality has become the main criteria for investment in corporate bonds. In the contemporary world, the Credit Rating Agency (CRAs) plays a crucial and important catalytic role in fostering the growth of the capital markets. A credit rating agency goes through thoroughly all the relevant information before it announces its rating value. The credit rating is expected to encapsulate the analysis of the finances of the company, its strengths and weaknesses, its competitive position in the industry, and its prospects. Thus, the Credit Rating Agency (CRAs) accesses the financial strength of the borrowers (issuers), especially their ability to pay the principal and interest on their debt⁵. Going further, under Regulation 13 read with the Code of Conduct Contained in the Third Schedule of the CRA Regulations⁶ provide for the principle-based benchmark for the conduct of credit rating agency. Some of the important codes of conduct in the aforementioned Third Schedule are as under Clause 1 requires a credit agency to make all efforts to protect the interest of investors. Clause 2 requires a credit rating agency to observe high standards of integrity, dignity, and fairness in the conduct of its business.

In different parts of the world, the status of the Credit Rating Agency's liability and their standard of care in respect of their activities diverges. Markedly, in India, there is a growing concern among the regulators about the credibility and reliability of Credit Rating Agency ratings. However, neither the regulations nor any notification or circular provides clients with a direct remedy to initiate litigation against CRAs providing incorrect ratings. While other countries increase the scope of liabilities of CRAs by making regulations and rules, India is quite different. For instance, in the European Union, a regulation⁷ was enacted in 2013 which imposed civil liability on the Credit Rating Agency. According to the regulations, liability goes to the extent of intent or gross negligence which causes damage to the investors who have relied on its ratings.

Recently, the Delhi High Court delineates and circumscribes the scope of liability in the case of *Jindal Power Limited v. ICRA Limited*⁸. The HC remarkably enumerated the grounds on which companies can challenge ratings issued by CRAs. The Court reasoned that CRAs provide expert opinion, with which the Court cannot interfere unless they are proved to be '*perverse, arbitrary and mala fide*'. Additionally, the case clarifies that CRAs are bound to observe the obligations as mentioned in the regulations and the same cannot be done away with by agreements concluded between the client and the CRA. This means that the court established the grounds for suing a Credit Rating Agency before the court in India. Hence, the parameter for the court to interfere and entertain the disputes arising out of rating are based on those three grounds. Thus, the purpose of this study is to analyze the significance and potential implications of providing '*perverse, arbitrary and mala fide*' as explicit grounds for challenging the ratings before the Court and its effects.

⁴ SUDHANSHU KUMAR & ALOK VERMA, GUIDE TO CAPITAL MARKET AND SECURITIES LAW pg. 217(Thomson Reuters)(2021)

⁵ ADJUDICATION ORDER IN RESPECT OF INDIA RATINGS & RESEARCH PRIVATE LIMITED IN THE MATTER OF RATING OF NCDS OF IL&FS. Page 36 of 53 (File No. EAD-/SS/AKS/74/146/2019-20)

⁶ Securities Exchange Board of India (Credit Rating Agencies) Regulations, 1999

⁷ Regulation (EU) No. 462/2013 of the European Parliament and the Council (2013)

⁸ CS(OS) 128/2020

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

In today's financial systems, CRAs play a critical role. Their major goal is to eliminate credit market information asymmetry by giving investors an opinion on an instrument's capacity to meet its responsibilities. CRAs believe that they deliver a more informed view since they have access to the company's management and confidential information about how it operates.

In India, the ratings provided by CRAs are considered an opinion based on the expert's reasonable judgment. **Nan S. Ellis et al**,⁹ commented on the liability of CRAs in the United State of America that accountants and other financial professionals play a similar duty to CRAs. CRAs employ their expertise to safeguard the public as well as investors by offering credit quality certification from a third party. CRAs, unlike accountants and other financial experts, have always been protected from liability when their ratings reflect inaccurate estimates of the investment's risk. The author explained civil liabilities which can be imposed on CRAs whereas, the authors stated that grounds for challenging rating of CRAs before the court are based on tort, for instance, negligence, fraud, and negligent misrepresentation. The authors did not explain the civil liability of CRAs and ground for challenging ratings before the court in other jurisdictions like India. However, their work has contributed to this study since it provided other grounds which can be considered by the court in finding CRAs liable regarding the inaccuracy of rating.

Furthermore, **Gerhard Oellinger et al**¹⁰ when addressing the inaccuracy of a credit rating and civil liability, the authors stated that when a rating's prediction about an issuer's or an issue rated's creditworthiness is not supported by facts, it is said to be incorrect. Two issues can arise in this regard: when the rating is overly good or when it is too negative. The last option is solely relevant to issuers, as it is in their best interests to acquire the highest possible rating. When the rating issued was greater than an accurate appraisal of the financial position justified, investors will lose money. This is because a high rating will persuade investors to believe that the product and/or the issuer are profitable, causing them to invest more money than they should.

Additionally, **Uwe Blaurock**¹¹, urged that even while these inaccuracies of a credit rating can happen and cause investors to lose money, they are not sources or grounds for civil liability. Indeed, investors must show more than a mismatch between the rating assigned and the factual reality to take CRAs to court, as this fact alone is not regarded as sufficient to establish culpability

The Securities Exchange Board of India (SEBI) has the authority to oversee the securities market in India. The SEBI (Credit Rating Agencies) Regulations, 1999, govern CRAs, and they have no direct liability to investors in the event of erroneous ratings. **Sudhanshu Kumar and Alok Verma**¹² in their book acknowledge the non-existence of guidelines of initiating civil liability against CRAs in India whereas they commented that regulatory action has been a major priority in India. even though CRAs have failed to act diligently in the recent past, there is no guidance on how dissatisfied investors should go about filing a civil claim.

Aline Darbellay¹³ urged on the importance of having civil liability against CRAs whereby the author commented that Civil liability is crucial for two reasons: first, it pays those who have been wronged, and second, it provides an incentive for CRAs to follow their legal obligations.

Thus, all of the above-mentioned papers and books explore various facets of the research project. As a result, they've been quite helpful in the process of examining numerous grounds for challenging CRAs before the court as well as the liability of CRAs. Hence, a few literary works from India were reviewed due to the uniqueness of the topic. Other jurisdictions' most relevant works were adopted.

4. BRIEF FACTS OF THE CASE

Jindal Power Limited v. ICRA Limited

In this case, Jindal Power Limited ('JPL') signed an agreement with ICRA in 2016 to rate the debt instruments it issued to banks in exchange for loans. According to the agreement, ICRA will be required to offer initial ratings when the company borrows money, as well as ratings during the surveillance period, which lasts until the debt is completely paid off. According to the contract, ICRA's professional responsibility was contingent on JPL's approval of the rating. During the early years of the surveillance era, JPL accepted both the initial and periodic ratings supplied by ICRA. However, a disagreement emerged between them over the April 2020 ratings. JPA

⁹ Nan S. Ellis, Lisa M. Fairchild & Frank D'Souza, *Is Imposing Liability on Credit Rating Agencies a Good Idea: Credit Rating Agency Reform in the Aftermath of the Global Financial Crisis*, 17 *Stan. J.L. Bus. & FIN.* 175 (2012).

¹⁰ GERHARD WILDMOSER; JAN SCHIFFER; BERND LANGOTH, 'HAFTUNG VON RATINGAGENTUREN GEGENÜBER ANLEGERN?', *RECHT DER INTERNATIONALEN WIRTSCHAFT*, 10 (2009)

¹¹ UWE BLAUROCK, 'CONTROL AND RESPONSIBILITY OF CREDIT RATING AGENCIES', *ELECTRONIC JOURNAL OF COMPARATIVE LAW*, 11.3 (2007)

¹² SUDHANSHU KUMAR & ALOK VERMA, *GUIDE TO CAPITAL MARKET AND SECURITIES LAW* pg. 237 (Thomson Reuters)(2021)

¹³ ALINE DARBELLAY, *REGULATING CREDIT RATING AGENCIES* (Cheltenham: Edward Elgar, 2013), at p. 76

declined to accept the ratings and requested that ICRA remove the ratings from its website and press release. Because ICRA refused to lower the ratings, JPL filed a petition with the HC, requesting that the credit rating rationales provided by ICRA be declared null, void, and unenforceable. The Court reasoned and held that CRAs provide expert opinions, which the Court cannot intervene with unless they are '**perverse, arbitrary, or mala fide**' because ICRA considered all relevant variables, the ratings they provided are reasonable, and hence cannot be called into question.

5. The legal implications of *perverse, arbitrary, and mala fide*

In India, the ratings provided by CRAs are considered as an opinion based on the expert's reasonable judgment. This has been stated in the case of **Jindal Power Limited v. ICRA Limited** hence, the Court will not consider whether the same is appropriate unless it is "**perverse, arbitrary, or mala fide**."

This position was inclined by the decision of the Supreme Court of India in the case of **Dr. Basavaiah vs Dr. H.L. Ramesh & ORS**¹⁴ whereby the court furthermore held that Courts in ordinary cases should avoid substituting their opinions for that of an expert. This position was influenced by the decision in the case of **The University of Mysore and Anr. v. C.D. Govinda Rao and Anr**¹⁵, in which the Constitution Bench unanimously held that usually, the Courts should be slow to interfere with the opinions expressed by the experts mostly in a case when there is no allegation of **mala fide** against the experts who had constituted the Selection Board. The court further observed that it would normally be wise and safe for the courts to leave the decisions of academic matters to the experts who are more familiar with the problems they face than the courts generally can be.

Under Regulation 29(2)(c) of the Securities and Exchange Board of India (Credit Rating Agencies) Regulations, 1999 empowers the board to investigate complaints received from investors, clients, or any other person on any matter having a bearing on activities of credit rating agency in so far as the complaints relate to the rating of securities that are listed or proposed to be listed on a stock exchange recognized by the Board. This means that the power of investigation by the Board under this clause is restricted to the complaints that relate to the rating of securities that are listed or proposed to be listed on an RSE. The same under Regulation 29 (4) provides for inspections to judge the appropriateness of the ratings only in case of complaints that are "**serious in nature**". Neither the Securities and Exchange Board of India nor the Securities and Exchange Board of India (Credit Rating Agencies) Regulations, 1999 defines the term '**serious nature**.' As a result, the regulator is limited in its ability to intervene in all situations of wrongdoing, only those that qualify to be termed as serious nature. Hence, no clear remedy is provided by the statutes in challenging the ratings in India.

In particular, the lack of a clear remedy prevents issuers from enforcing CRA responsibilities owing to them. The High Court has provided some clarity to the ambiguities surrounding the term 'serious nature' by stating specific grounds. Given the subjective nature of the terms "**perverse, arbitrary, or mala fide**," the matter may require additional litigation to determine the effectiveness of the grounds and guarantee that the exceptions carved out are not abused. This is due to the fact that there's no clear meaning as to what constitutes **perverse, arbitrary, or mala fide** regarding the actions of CRAs as far as rating is concerned.

Moreover, declaring **perverse, arbitrary, and mala fide** as the explicit ground limits the jurisdiction of the court to entertain the matter arising out of rating such as tortious liability. It's upon an aggrieved person of the rating to confine his or her cause of action in those three grounds regardless of its nature.

Furthermore, the concurrent jurisdiction of the SEBI and civil courts in situations relating to ratings may result in forum shopping and conflict of jurisdiction. However, a credible threat of legal action might considerably improve credit rating independence, impartiality, and accountability.

6. GROUNDS FOR CHALLENGING RATINGS IN ANOTHER JURISDICTION

6.1 GROUNDS FOR SUIT AGAINST CRAS IN THE U.S.A

In other jurisdictions, the grounds for challenging rating of CRAs before the court are widely whereby a suit can be brought under tort law for instance misrepresentation, negligence, and fraud or contract law. Plaintiffs must show that the CRA made a statement of facts than expressions of opinion to launch a claim for fraud or negligent misrepresentation. However, this position has been confronted by the CRAs whereas ratings, according to CRAs, are not a factual statement but rather nonactionable forecasts of the future. Several courts have concurred with this position. For instance, in the case of **Jefferson County School District v. Moody's Investors Services**,¹⁶ the court ruled out that ratings are neither opinions nor factual facts. Only statements which can be proven false are actionable. The same decision was reiterated in the case of **Compuware Corp. v. Moody's Investor Services**.

¹⁴ Dr. Basavaiah vs Dr. H.L. Ramesh & ORS Civil Appeal No. 6057 of 2010

¹⁵ The University of Mysore and Anr. v. C.D. Govinda Rao and Anr. AIR 1965 SC 491,

¹⁶ Jefferson County School District v. Moody's Investors 988 F. Supp. 1341 (D. Colo. 1997)

Furthermore, in the case of **Abu Dhabi Commercial Bank v. Morgan Stanley & Co**¹⁷. In this case, Abu Dhabi Commercial Bank sued the defendant following the collapse of a special purpose vehicle (SPV). Their allegation was based upon negligence, negligent misrepresentation, and fraud. The court held that even if the statements were classified as opinions, they were still actionable because the CRAs knew that these opinions were misleading investors.

6.2 Under European CRA Regulations

The European legislature agreed to take steps to make CRAs more accountable to issuers and investors. Under Article 35a (1) of the CRA (Civil Liability) Regulations of 2013 provides that where a CRA has committed intentionally or with gross negligence, any of the infringements listed in Annexure III having an impact on the rating, an investor or issuer may claim damages from the CRA for damages caused to it due to that infringement. Annexure III list out different types of infringements including failure to use information that according to its methods is important, failure to use rigorous, systematic, continuous methodologies that are subject to validation based on historical experience, including backtesting.

An investor can claim damages under Article 35a (1) where it establishes that it has reasonably relied, under Article 5a(1) or otherwise with due care, on a credit rating for a decision to invest into, hold onto or divest from a financial instrument covered by that credit rating. An issuer can claim damages under Article 35a (1) where it establishes that it or its financial instruments are covered by that credit rating and the infringement was not caused by misleading and inaccurate information provided by the issuer to the credit rating agency, directly or through information publicly available¹⁸.

Furthermore, the competent national court is vested with powers to determine what constitutes accurate and detailed information, taking into account that the investor or issuer may not have access to information that is solely within the credit rating agency's sphere of influence.

6.3 AUSTRALIA

Bathurst Regional Council v Local Government Financial Services Pty Ltd was a landmark case¹⁹. Standard & Poor's was declared accountable for the damages sustained by investors by the Federal Court of Australia. The claimants made investments in sophisticated financial instruments (known as "Constant Proportionate Debt Obligations") that were rated AAA by S&P, but they eventually lost the majority of their money. S&P had negligently breached a duty of care to investors, according to the court.

7. CONCLUSION

CRAs play a crucial catalytic role in fostering the growth of the capital markets in India. Essentially, the High Court has assured that clients (issuers and investors) are protected from faulty and incorrect credit ratings by identifying particular reasons for challenging credit ratings issued by CRAs. Despite anything included in the CRA-client agreement to the contrary, the decision underscores that CRAs are expected to fulfill their statutory obligations. Also, this can be a leeway for issuers and investors to challenge ratings under civil liability actions such as tortious action and contractual liability. The solution to the uncertainty of CRAs liability is to create a specific rule or to modify the CRA Regulation which will specifically provide the remedy and grounds for challenging ratings.

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¹⁷ Abu Dhabi Commercial Bank v. Morgan Stanley & Co 08 Civ. 7508 (SAS)

¹⁸ Annex III, I.6, CRA Regulation

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